

UTERINE MYOMA — DIAGNOSIS, CONSERVATIVE AND OPERATIVE TREATMENT.

Kurbanova Surayyo Ilxom qizi

Obstetrician-gynecologist of the 4th family polyclinic
of Mirzo Ulugbek district

kurbanovasurayyo1992@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

What is uterine myoma, why does it appear, myoma treatment with conservative and surgical methods, and what are its symptoms? This article contains the necessary answers to all the above questions.

Uterine myoma is a chronic multifactorial disease in which nodules of smooth muscle cells with unpredictable growth dynamics are formed in the wall of the organ. This condition occurs in many women, it is not life-threatening, but it can cause unpleasant symptoms and interfere with the beginning of pregnancy. In this article, we will tell you how to identify myoma at the initial stage, in what cases it should be treated, and which methods of therapy are the most effective. Diagnosis of uterine fibroids

Imaging techniques (ultrasound, physiological infusion sonography or MRI) If significant changes are detected during bimanual gynecological examination: diagnosis of uterine myoma: enlarged, mobile, irregular uterus. Imaging techniques are required for confirmation and are usually indicated in the following cases:

- In recurrent myoma.
- When fibroids increase in size.

- When causing symptoms.
- To distinguish them from other abnormalities (for example, ovarian tumors).

If a diagnostic examination is needed, in most cases ultrasound or saline sonography is used. In saline infusion sonography, a saline solution is injected into the uterine cavity. This allows more accurate diagnosis of myoma in the uterus during ultrasound. If ultrasound examination, including sonography with physiological infusion (when performing this method), is inconclusive, MRI, which is usually the most accurate method of diagnostic imaging, is performed.

Treatment of uterine fibroids

- Gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) agonists or other drugs may be used for temporary relief of symptoms.
 - Myomectomy (to preserve fertility) or hysterectomy to treat symptomatic fibroids
- Asymptomatic fibroids do not require treatment. Patients should be examined

periodically (every 6-12 months). Symptomatic fibroid treatments, including ovarian suppression to stop bleeding, are ineffective and of limited use. However, before the operation, the doctor must first consider the possibility of medical treatment. GnRH agonists can be prescribed before surgery to reduce the size of the fibrous tissue; these drugs often stop menstruation and increase the general blood analysis index. In menopausal women, recovery can usually be expected, as symptoms may disappear over time as fibroids shrink after menopause.

Treatment of uterine fibroids without surgery

In some cases, uterine fibroids can be treated without surgery.

Foot ablation

FUT-ablation (fuz-ablation) or focused ultrasound ablation is an advanced method of non-surgical treatment of uterine fibroids. The principle of treatment is coagulation of myomatous nodes in the uterus using focused ultrasound (FUT) pulses. Control of the direction and level is carried out in real time with the help of MRT. This procedure is much safer and more convenient than the operation to remove fibroids. Unfortunately, FUT treatment is effective only for certain types of fibroids, so the decision to treat each patient is strictly individualized. The advantages of this method are:

- In the absence of injury, blood loss, the procedure is performed under the influence of light sedative drugs;
- Maintaining the integrity of the uterus and, as a result, reproductive ability;
- Highly effective method;
- Few side effects;
- Prevention of recurrence;
- Quick recovery times (treatment can be performed without hospitalization).

Principles of conservative treatment of uterine fibroids

In order to get rid of myoma without surgical intervention, it is necessary to follow the principles of correct nutrition, hormonal and immune status recovery. In addition, it is recommended to take phytopreparations and homeopathic remedies. How to treat uterine fibroids without surgery? The main measures to eliminate myoma include:

- Treatment and prevention of sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) and microflora disorders of the genitals;
- Restoration and stimulation of immunity;
- Correcting the diet aimed at normalizing metabolism;
- Working with the patient's psychoemotional condition;
- Normalization of the menstrual cycle, elimination of uterine bleeding, measures against anemia.

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